

Synthesis, spectral characterization and anti-microbial screening of some novel 1, 2, 4- dithiazole bearing coumarin moiety.

K. U. Dongare^{a*}, S. A. Waghmare^b, S. B. Sarkate^c, R. N. Ingole^d

^{a,b,c}-Department of Chemistry, Ghulam Nabi Azad Arts, Commerce and Science College
Barshitakli Dist. Akola 444401 (M.S.), India

^d-Department of Chemistry, Shri Vitthal Rukhmini College, Sawana, Mahagaon,
Dist. Yavatmal, (M.S.), India

*Corresponding author- K. U. Dongare

ABSTRACT

One step synthesis of 7-(3-substitutedimino-1,2,4-dithiazolo)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**IIa-e**) was carried out by oxidative cyclisation of 7-(5-substituted-2,4-dithiobiureto)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Ia-e**) by using liquid bromine in chloroform medium as an oxidizing agent. The synthesized compounds from these reaction conditions were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, chemical characteristic and IR, PMR MASS, spectral data and antimicrobial activity against gram positive and gram-negative bacteria such as *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. aerogenes*, *B. subtilis* and *B. megatherium*. etc.

Keywords: 7-(5-substituted-2,4-dithiobiureto)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one, liquid bromine, chloroform, ammonium hydroxide ethanol, gram positive and gram-negative bacteria etc.

INTRODUCTION

Organic compounds containing thiadiazol¹ as the heterocycles in their structure are identified for their biological activities, pharmaceutical activities, industrial applications, agricultural purposes and in medicinal sciences²⁻³. Basically, structure of thiadiazol is five member nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocyclic compound. Presence of sulphur and nitrogen in its structure enhances the biological potential of the thiadiazol. Kalogirou⁴ had reported 1,2,3-dithiazole for the antimicrobial activities, Laitinen *et al.*⁵ reported the 1,2,3-dithiazole for the antibacterial activities, Matysiak⁶ had reported thiadiazol and some different substituents attached thiadiazol directly or indirectly shows effect directly in their biological, medicinal property.

Similarly, Sayed⁷ has prepared the thiadiazol based coumarin the best antimicrobial activities. The biological as well as industrial applications of coumarin⁸ get enhanced due the presence of the thiadiazol nucleus in their structure. This 1,2,4-dithiazole synthesis technique is quicker, less complicated, less expensive and requires less time.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

All the chemical used were of loba chemie (AR grade).

Method:

In the present experiment for the synthesis of different substituted 7-(3-substitutedimino-1,2,4-dithiazolo)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one by using liquid bromine in chloroform medium. Reaction mixture was kept at room conditions for 4 hours.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used for the synthesis must be purified. After refluxing the purity of the compounds were checked by TLC (aluminium TLC) with thin layer thickness of 200 um. The melting points of all synthesise compounds will be recorded using hot paraffin bath. The carbon and hydrogen analysis were carried out on Carlo-Ebra-1106 analyser Nitrogen estimation were carried out with colmon-N-analyzer-29. IR spectra were recorded with Bruker spectrometer in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . PMR spectra were recorded on VARIAN 400 MHz spectrometer with TMS as internal standard using CDCl_3 and DMSO Solvent.

GENERAL PROCEDURE

In a clean China dish paste of 7-(5-substituted-2,4-dithiobiureto)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Ia-e**) was prepared in chloroform and 5% liquid bromine in chloroform (2 ml) was added with constant stirring at room conditions. During the addition of bromine solution to firstly the colour of bromine disappear, addition of bromine was continued till colour of bromine appears and persists to the paste. Reaction mixture was kept for 4 hours at room conditions. On basification of the reaction mixture with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution, pale yellow solid of (**IIa-e**) obtained.

Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of all the derivatives in the series. The tentative reaction for the formation of product is depicted below,

Reaction

Similarly, 4-methyl-7-{[3-(phenylimino)-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino}-2H-chromen-2-one (**IIb**), 7-{[3-(*tert*-butylimino)-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino}-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**IIc**), 4-methyl-7-({3-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl}amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (**IId**) and 7-({3-[(4-chlorophenyl)imino]-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl}amino)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**IIe**) were synthesized from the oxidative cyclisation 7-(5-phenyl-2,4-dithiobiureto)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Ib**), 7-(5-*tert*-butyl-2,4-dithiobiureto)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Ic**), 7-[5-(4-methylphenyl)-2,4-dithiobiureto]-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Id**) and 7-[5-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,4-dithiobiureto]-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**Ie**) with liquid bromine in chloroform medium respectively by the above mentioned procedure.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Spectral characterization results for all the synthesized compounds are given below

Spectral Characterization

1) 7-{[3-(Ethylimino)-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino}-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (**IIa**)

Yellow solid, C₁₄H₁₃N₃O₂S₂, Yield-87%, M.P.-142 °C. %Composition found (**calculated**): C-52.59(52.64), H-4.07(4.10), N-13.14(13.15), O-10.01(10.01) and S-20.03(20.07). **IR spectrum (cm⁻¹)**: 3130.50 (Ar C-H stretching), 1140.12(C=S stretching), 3340.43 (NH stretching) and 1740.41 (C=O stretch lactone). **PMR spectrum**: The spectrum of a compound was carried out in CDCl₃. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to

singlet 3 protons of -CH₃ gives singlet at δ 2.4 ppm due to attachment with aromatic ring, 3 protons of -CH= of aromatic ring gives doublet at δ 7.7, 7.74 and 7.3 ppm, 1 proton of -CH= of conjugated lactone gives singlet at δ 5.84 ppm, 2 protons of -CH₂ gives quartet at δ 3.5 ppm, 3 protons of -CH₃ gives triplet at δ 1.38 ppm, 1 proton -NH attached between thionyl group and phenyl ring also deshielded due to thioamide position and gives signal at δ 3.9 ppm. **Mol. Wt.:** 319.40.

2) 4-Methyl-7-[[3-(phenylimino)-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino]-2H-chromen-2-one (IIb)

Yellow solid, C₁₈H₁₃N₃O₂S₂, Yield-85%, M.P.-134 °C. **%Composition found (calculated):** C-58.78(58.83), H-3.53(3.56), N-11.43(11.43), O-8.70(8.70) and S-17.41(17.45). **IR spectrum (cm⁻¹):** 3050.12 (Ar C-H stretching), 1090.06 (C=S stretching), 3400.12 (NH stretching), 1753.94 (C=O stretch lactone) and 1580.29 (NH bending). **PMR spectrum:** The spectrum of a compound was carried out in CDCl₃. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to singlet 3 protons of -CH₃ gives singlet at δ 2.4 ppm due to attachment with aromatic ring, 4 protons of -CH= of aromatic ring gives doublet at δ 7.7, 7.3, 7.4 and 7.6 ppm, 1 proton of -CH= of conjugated lactone gives singlet at δ 5.85 ppm, 1 proton -NH attached between thionyl group and phenyl ring also deshielded due to thioamide position and gives signal at δ 3.8 ppm. **Mol. Wt.:** 367.44.

3) Synthesis of 7-[[3-(tert-butylimino)-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino]-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one(IIc)

Yellow amorphous solid, C₁₆H₁₇N₃S₂O₂, yield 85%, M.P. 110 °C, **% Composition found (calculated),** C-55.33(55.33), H-4.94(4.93), N-12.09(12.09), O-9.20(9.20), S-18.45(18.45). **IR spectrum (cm⁻¹):** 3450.12 (N-H stretching), 3034.72 (C-H Ar Stretching), 1560.56 (N-H Bending), 1120.12 (C=S stretching) and 1740.40 C=O stretching(lactone). **PMR spectrum:** The spectrum of a compound was carried out in CDCl₃. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to singlet of 3H of -(CH₃) at δ 2.42 ppm, singlet of 9H of -(CH₃)₃ at δ 1.35 ppm, singlet of 1H of -CH= of conjugated lactone gives singlet at δ 5.8 ppm, 3 protons of -CH= of aromatic benzene ring gives doublet at δ 7.7, 7.4 and 7.7 ppm and singlet of -NH at δ 3.4 ppm. **Mol. Wt.:** 347.45.

4) 4-Methyl-7-([3-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl]amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (II d)

Yellow solid, C₁₉H₁₅N₃O₂S₂, Yield-88%, M.P.-118 °C. **%Composition found (calculated):** C-59.76(59.82), H-3.93(3.96), N-11.01(11.01), O-8.38(8.38) and S-19.77(16.81). **IR spectrum (cm⁻¹):** 3052.15 (Ar C-H stretching), 1050.20 (C=S stretching), 3470.12 (NH stretching), 1735.12 (C=O stretch lactone), 1570.12 (NH

bending) and 2930.52 C-H (CH₃ stretching). **PMR spectrum:** The spectrum of a compound was carried out in CDCl₃. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to singlet 3 protons of -CH₃ gives singlet at δ 2.4 and 2.02 ppm due to attachment with aromatic ring, 5 protons of -CH= of aromatic ring gives doublet at δ 7.2, 7.7, 7.03, 7.3 and 7.6 ppm, 1 proton of -CH= of conjugated lactone gives singlet at δ 5.8 ppm, 1 proton -NH attached between thionyl group and phenyl ring also deshielded due to thioamide position and gives signal at δ 3.5 ppm. **Mol. Wt.:** 381.47.

5) 7-({3-[(4-Chlorophenyl)imino]-1,2,4-dithiazol-5-yl}amino)-4-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (IIe)

Yellow solid, C₁₈H₁₂N₃O₂S₂Cl, Yield-84%, M.P.-130 °C. **%Composition found (calculated):** C-53.74(553.79), H-2.98(3.009), N-10.45 (10.45), O-7.96(7.95) and S-15.92(15.95). **IR spectrum (cm⁻¹):** 3080.45 (Ar C-H stretching), 1160.50 (C=S stretching), 3470.15 (NH stretching), 1745.12 (C=O stretch lactone), 1570.01 (NH bending) and 2950.63 C-H (CH₃ stretching). **PMR spectrum:** The spectrum of a compound was carried out in CDCl₃. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to singlet 3 protons of -CH₃ gives singlet at δ 2.3 ppm due to attachment with aromatic ring, 4 protons of -CH= of aromatic ring gives doublet at δ 7.29, 7.78, 7.54, 7.35 and 7.60 ppm, 1 proton of -CH= of conjugated lactone gives singlet at δ 5.86 ppm, 1 proton -NH attached between thionyl group and phenyl ring also deshielded due to thioamide position and gives signal at δ 3.5 ppm. **Mol. Wt.:** 401.88.

PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES

Antimicrobial Activity

All the synthesized compounds (**II-a**) to (**II-e**) were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. aerogenes*, *B. subtilis* and *B. megatherium*. by disc diffusion method was performed using Mueller Hinton agar as well as nutrient agar medium. Each and every compound was tested at conc. 50 μ g/ml in ethanol. The zone of inhibition of all the synthesized compounds were measured after 24-hour incubation at 37 °C. Standard drug used for comparison the activity was Ciprofloxacin.

CONCLUSION

In the present research work is cheaper and less time-consuming method for synthesis of organic compound (**IIa-e**). In all the synthesized compounds give the maximum yield of product (**II a-e**). All the synthesized coumarin based 1,2,4-dithiazole derivative (**IIa-e**) shows good antimicrobial activity against various bacteria's such as *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. aerogenes*, *B. subtilis* and *B. megatherium*.

Table 1: Synthesized compound **IIa-e** activity against Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria.

Table No. 1.1– Antimicrobial sensitivity test against bacteria (after 24 hours at 37 °C temp.) (zone of inhibition in mm)							
SR No .	Compd.	Gram positive			Gram negative		
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. megatherium</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>A. aerogenes</i>
11	KUD-IIa	12	00	12	12	00	12
12	KUD-IIb	14	12	14	14	12	16
13	KUD-IIc	12	14	00	14	00	16
14	KUD-IId	14	14	11	14	14	11
15	KUD-IIe	18	14	11	16	12	12
27	Standard Ciprofloxacin	18	20	22	24	16	12

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